

INSIDE THE CLASSROOM WALLS: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF SECONDARY TEACHERS IN IMPOSING CLASSROOM DISCIPLINE IN LIGHT OF CHILD PROTECTION POLICY

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Inside the Classroom Walls: Lived Experiences of Secondary Teachers in Imposing Classroom Discipline in Light of Child Protection Policy

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the experiences of teachers in imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy. The researcher also identified the challenges and coping mechanisms when implementing the policy. The research employed qualitative research methods using phenomenological approach. The participants of the study were fourteen teachers who are bona fide high school teacher of Sagayen National High School. Based on the findings, the researcher found that the participants had to be flexible in challenges and changes. It was revealed that teachers were facing parental resistance and lack of support from parents. However, it was also revealed that teachers were adjusting their disciplinary methods to comply with the mandates of the child protection policy. Some of the participants answered that in imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy, they must explore diverse resources for guidance, wisdom and support, implement reinforcement and constructive feedback, stay calm and focused, and seek assistance and guidance from colleagues. Moreover, this is a phenomenological study in which elicitation techniques were examined and explored. Nonetheless, reflecting on the process and techniques used in the utilization of abstract here can help to operationalize them in the future use.

Keywords: *Child Protection Policy, phenomenological, teachers, classroom, study, discipline, Philippines*

Introduction

The best way to protect children is to empower them to protect themselves. Teachers are considered as the second parents of the children or students who guide them so that they will not be misled. In today's generation, children are getting worst such as exposing poor attitude, disrespectful and impoliteness because they rely on their rights that teachers cannot impose corporal punishments, hurt them physically, emotionally and even mentally. Teachers cannot force the children to obey and mandates them to do what he/she wanted to do so. Also, teachers are having difficulties in shaping children's good character and moral dilemma. Abandoned or neglected children are those who do not get proper, regular and good care and attention, love and direction at physical, psychological and social level by their families or by primary caregivers who are supposed to act as parents on behalf of families and who are to be held accountable for their welfare and growth (Saragih & Mardianto, 2019).

Indeed, in Australia, existing studies in countries of different regions suggest that children who receive any type of maltreatment are more likely to develop learning problems that result in poor academic performance, grade retention and special education placement. Further, seven abuse cases are reported on average per day in Malaysia in the year 2008. The common forms of child abuse are neglect, beatings, physical and sexual abuse. The percentage of mothers who abused their children was higher than the percentage of fathers who abused the minor. However, there were probably thousands of other such incidents that were never reported because they were either too awkward (Nikku & Azman, 2017).

However, major threats to children's wellbeing in the Philippines include widespread emotional and psychological abuse, physical punishment, and familial violence. Additionally, the child protection system is referred to as being tip-down, with clear national policy and regulation that is being applied so shoddily that its systematic qualities are called into question. While social welfare infrastructure lacks capacity and technical skills, child protection coverage varies greatly in terms of resources and approaches (Roche et al., 2021; UNICEF 2016).

The researcher decided to do this study so that she could get baseline information about how would secondary teachers impose discipline with their students and examine their challenges in imposing discipline in light of Child Protection Policy. By examining teachers' perspectives on the implementation of child protection policies, the study can shed light on how discipline issues could be handled in a way that was consistent with the policy. In this regard, the study also touches on the issue of discipline in classrooms, which was a growing concern in the educational system. Secondary teachers are the subject of the study, which is crucial because they were in charge of educating children during a crucial time in their development. Understanding their opinions on the application of child protection policies could help to raise educational standards and safeguard student safety. Therefore, the study was vital and crucial because it can provide light on secondary teachers' perspectives, experiences, and difficulties with regard to enforcing classroom rules and child safety policies. It can assist raise educational standards and safeguard students' safety. Besides, the results of this study would help and guide secondary teachers in developing their skills in teaching in discipline.

The issue of the classroom discipline in light of child protection policy lacks national study. For instance, Al-Qaysi (2018)'s study entitled "The Impact of Child Protection Policy on Omani Classrooms", results indicated a statistical significant difference among the staff members' attitudes where females were more positive towards the adoption of the child protection policy rather than males. On the other hand, the study of Castino, (2023)'s study entitled "Child Protection Policy and Behavioral Management Practices at a Public

Elementary School in Rizal, Philippines", study determined the child protection policy and behavioral management practices of a public elementary school in Rizal, Philippines in the year 2018-2019. In addition, the study of Roche, (2021) entitled "Local Child Protection in the Philippines: A Case Study of Actors, Processes and Key Risks for Children," explores the child protection actors, processes and child maltreatment issues in a regional Local Government Unit in the Philippines. However, in this study, it would uncover the perspectives of teachers regarding the classroom discipline in light of child protection policy and examine their experience, challenges and insights.

In this study, the research findings will be disseminated through the distribution of copies of research papers, reports, or concise summaries to relevant stakeholders, collaborators, and community members. This dissemination approach aims to facilitate accessibility for key individuals, enabling them to actively participate in understanding the important findings of the research. By providing physical copies of research papers, the researcher aims to broaden the impact and significance of the study within academic, collaborative, and community contexts.

Research Questions

This study aimed to identify the perspectives of the Secondary Teachers in imposing discipline towards on the implementation of Child Protection Policy. Moreover, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of secondary teachers in imposing discipline in light of the child protection policy?
2. How do the secondary teachers cope up with the challenges in imposing discipline in light of the child protection policy?
3. What are the insights of secondary teachers in imposing discipline in light of the child protection policy?

Methodology

Research Design

This paper used a qualitative research method of data collection and analysis, which focused on the collection of non-numeric data to understand concepts, perceptions or attitudes. It may be used to identify nuanced information about an issue or to develop new research ideas. Quantitative research was an approach that occurred in real-life and was not hypothesis driven. The data collected was looked at in terms of meaning and context and was presented in a descriptive form and no numerical data were used. The main focus is to describe the patterns and changes that take place in the field of study under consideration (Bhandari, 2020).

A qualitative approach was the most appropriate approach for this study because of its data collection process which was through gathering subjective experiences from the participants and the way how data is interpret. Since this study focuses on the experiences, coping mechanisms and insights of the secondary teachers in imposing discipline inside the classroom walls in light of child protection policy. This qualitative research design would allow the researcher to gather significant information from the participant's point of view which was very crucial for this study.

There were various methods used in this qualitative research, such as group discussion to explore ideas and behaviors, semi-structured interviews to gather information on the specific subjects, in-depth interviews to gain insight into personal experiences and examination of written material such as official documents, news articles, and personal journals to gain knowledge about both public and private perspectives (Hammarberg et al., 2016). Additionally, qualitative research design provides researcher a valuable benefit as the use of qualitative research methods allows researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of their subject matter, which cannot be attained easily through surveys that use only close-ended questions. Qualitative techniques provide a flexible and dynamic approach to research, as it allows the researchers to delve deeper into the responses given by the participants and explore the subject matter in more depth during the research process, in contrast to a structured survey where this level of engagement is not possible (Tiley, 2017).

These qualitative research techniques were applied to this study as the researcher engage in in-depth interviews with the participants which was an opportunity for the researcher to uncovered the issues in order to obtain detailed results. Moreover, the qualitative research design enabled the researcher to gain relevant and varying information from the participants considering the fact that they had different experiences and challenges in real world setting which are beneficial for secondary teachers for better understanding in imposing discipline inside the classroom walls of in light of child protection policy.

Participants

In this phenomenological study, the key participants were the secondary teachers among the province of Davao del Norte. Fourteen participants were carefully selected in the research endeavor. Fourteen (14) of which undergo an in-depth interview (IDI) each of them was interviewed individually by the researcher through face-to-face set up. And the researcher would make sure that the ambiance was suits for the discussion and the location was free from distractions. With that, the participants feel at ease in giving their responses.

To ensure the confidentiality the researcher ensured that the informed consent is given them and they agree in the ground of interview. This was to establish the rapport between the interviewer and the participants. The names of the participants was purposely obscured. Each participant was given an assumed or pseudonyms so as not to reveal their true identities for ethical considerations.

Better data was obtained through a qualitative research study with fewer than 20 participants. A smaller group made it simpler for the

researcher to establish deep bonds with the participants, which results in more organic conversations and superior data (Crouch & McKenzie, 2006).

Upon the participants' selection, purposive sampling was to ensure that only those who gave necessary data would be able to participate in my study. Purposive sampling applied which highly relies on the set of inclusion criteria. This sampling method was a non-probability type of sampling which guarantees the acquisition of authentic lived experiences. This guaranteed as the sampling method employs participants who were closely immersed or involved in the phenomenon being investigated (Ellis, 2016).

In the recruitment process, the researcher religiously followed the succeeding criteria. Firstly, each participant must be a junior high school teacher in Davao del Norte. Secondly, the participant must be at 10 years and above in teaching or in service. Lastly, each participant must be teaching in public schools.

Procedure

The researcher employed different steps in data collection as well as gathering relevant information for the study. In conducting the study, the researcher has considered safety protocols such as social distancing, wearing of face masks, as well as bringing alcohol since the pandemic was still ongoing. This is to ensure full safety and protection of the participants and other involved individuals while conducting the study.

In collecting the data, the researcher went through several steps and measures which were specified below. This was to make sure that the findings of this study would gain ethical soundness and a high extent of trustworthiness.

First, the researcher submitted her manuscript for it to be checked by the research technical panel. There were lots of corrections and changes with the manuscripts but eventually, the panel members gave their approvals for her to gather the data needed. Afterwards, the researcher would write a permission letter addressed to the institution where she conducted her study.

After writing the permission letter, the researcher personally went to the school where she would conduct her study. She secured first the signature of her research adviser as well as the signature of the research director before going to the College President for the approval. Afterwards, she identified her research participants using the purposive sampling technique.

On another note, the participants were selected based on the following criteria: (1) each participant must be a junior high school teacher in Davao del Norte: (2) the participant must be at 10 years and above in teaching or service: (3) each participant must be teaching in public schools.

Second, the participants were asked to read and understand first the consent and agreement form that were handed out by the researcher before they can sign it. This is to ensure that the participants were willing to share their knowledge and experiences to the researcher for the completion of the study.

Third, the participants were oriented about the study. The orientation includes the purpose of the interview, information regarding the confidentiality of the data that they gave, as well as the benefits that they gained in cooperating with the researcher. Moreover, the researcher was made sure that both of them, the participants and researcher, had their own share of benefits in this study.

Fourth, in interviewing, the researcher recorded their conversation with the participants. Since we were free to go outside and communicate others without hesitation that may virus spread, the interview is conducted face-to-face for the IDI. However, the participants and interviewer still carefully communicate to the interviewee's, therefore, she would still make wear of face mask and use alcohol for sanitation. These video conferencing services has a feature wherein the conference was recorded automatically which was very useful during interviews.

Fifth, the researcher transcribed the collected information before translating it from raw language to Standard English language. After translating the data, the researcher identified the themes as well as the principles of thematic analysis. Finally, the researcher seeks for assistance of a data analyst through handing out the themes that had been identified for analysis.

Data Analysis

This paper used a qualitative research method of data collection and analysis, which focused on the collection of non-numeric data to understand concepts, perceptions or attitudes. It may be used to identify nuanced information about an issue or to develop new research ideas. Quantitative research was an approach that occurred in real-life and was not hypothesis driven. The data collected was looked at in terms of meaning and context and was presented in a descriptive form and no numerical data were used. The main focus is to describe the patterns and changes that take place in the field of study under consideration (Bhandari, 2020).

The methodical search and organizing of Interview transcripts, observation notes, or other non-textual elements was known as qualitative data analysis. This technique was carried out to give the researcher the opportunity to collect information and improve public understanding of the phenomena or study subject. (Luna & Beng, 2017).

The responses of the study's participants were collected, transcribed, and then translated from their native languages into Standard English. These transcripts served as the major data source for this study's analysis. The data was subjected to a number of treatments

and processing stages before being used to draw findings from the study.

The replies from the participants in this study were collected, transcribed, and then translated from their original languages into Standard English. The primary source of data for this study's data analysis were these transcripts. To extract the study's conclusions, the data underwent a number of treatments and processing steps.

The researcher's subsequent step was to conduct a qualitative topic analysis. Thematic analysis is one of the most common methods of analysis used in qualitative research. It involves reading over a data set, such as transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups, and looking for patterns in meaning to extract themes. Thematic analysis is an active reflective process in which the researcher's personal experience is critical for deriving meaning from the data. When finding trends in data, learning about qualitative analysis, and engaging research subjects in the analysis process, thematic analysis should be considered (Delve, 2020).

In this study, the researcher classified the themes for analysis. She looked for parallels among the ideas or codes that emerged from the codification process. At this moment, key themes emerged. These topics were used to create the overall description of the phenomenon under study. The study's themes were thoroughly explored and built upon to create a detailed depiction, allowing the researcher to draw conclusions and verify them.

Finally, data reduction was performed to analyze the data. This means that useless data is deleted and modified into valuable material for the purposes of the investigation. This was to make the facts comprehensible to the readers (Sutton & Austin, 2015).

In this study, the researcher began by reviewing all collected data to identify which parts were essential for answering the research questions and which could be set aside. This initial review involved sorting through transcripts and notes from the interviews, highlighting key themes, significant quotes, and important observations. By doing so, the researcher could filter out repetitive or off-topic information, making it easier to concentrate on the insights that truly mattered.

To further enhance this process, the researcher enlisted the help of a data analyst, an expert in organizing and managing data. The data analyst played a vital role in merging, sorting, and categorizing the relevant information. This collaboration allowed for a more systematic approach to data reduction, ensuring that the final dataset was well-organized and ready for deeper analysis. The analyst helped to create a clearer structure, making it easier to identify patterns and themes within the data.

Ethical Considerations

Individuals who were students in general were the study's major focus. In order to maintain their trust in us, the researcher guaranteed their safety and provided them with complete protection. The researcher also adheres to the following ethical principles when conducting research: respect for individuals, goodness, fairness, consent, and secrecy (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons was the researcher's obligation to exploit the weaknesses of the research participants, self-sufficiency will prohibit to maintain trust, friendship, and confidence among participants and the researcher. Prior to the administration of interviews, the researcher asks permission from the principal and the participants itself and she adjust upon their availability. Therefore, she set interview schedule ahead of time. This was ensured that the researcher would not be a reason that her participants may have to absent from their respective classes; also, to avoid delay or cancellation of their important errands.

Before the gathering of data, the researcher contacted first her participants regarding her study. She informs them about her research and she make sure they are willing to share their experiences with her. The researcher also informed them that she will be recording the whole conversation.

However, she will not proceed with the interview right after receiving their agreement. Since her participants are teachers, she presumed that they have busy schedules. Hence, to avoid any conflicts with their time, the researcher asks them when they are vacant for her to set a specific date and time for the interview.

Moreover, the researcher certainly makes sure that the participants will not be harmed physically and psychologically in her study. Also, she makes certain that she referred to her panel of examinees with regards to all the steps that she takes prior to the conduct of her study in order to have an appropriate procedure of collecting the data. Furthermore, the researcher hereby disclosed that her participants are in no way vulnerable to coercion or any sort of exploitation by the principal investigator. Respect shall be highly acknowledged.

Benevolence requires commitment to minimize participant risks rather than maximizing gains owing to them. In order to protect each participant from risk, the interviewee's anonymity will be maintained. Participants will always be protected, and no information file will ever be unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007)

This study would make sure that the participants had their own share of benefits as these generate insights and coping mechanisms that can be useful in improving the life of student parents in general. Participants will be able to share their experiences and insights, at the same time they can be able to learn how others will cope up with their challenges. In addition, the researcher ensures that her participants will not be expose in any risk during the conduct of this study.

Consent is another approach to demonstrate respect for the informants in the research. This is to ensure that all participants understand

the objectives and purpose of the research that they will be involved in. They are given written authorization that confirms their approval: once approved, they participate in the in-depth interviews. Of course, they were informed about the outcomes and findings of the study (Creswell, 2012).

Before the conduct of this study, the researcher makes sure that her participants are willing to share their experiences. She informs them with the benefits they will gain in participating in this study as well as how they can be able to contribute for the improvement of the life of other student parents. She provides an information sheet in order for the participants to be aware.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of this study were secondary teachers coming from Sagayan National High School. As illustrated in Table 1, there were 14 secondary teachers, they were all undergone in-depth interview and at least 10 years in service or more. They were all 14 in total, of which 6 were males and 8 were females. They were chosen based on the criteria and they were able to meet it.

In-depth Interview there were fourteen key informants in this study, six male and eight female. Following the principle of confidentiality, each participant for the in-depth interview was assigned a pseudonym during the interview, as used by Bernal (2014) Assignment of pseudonyms was made according to their unique role, characteristics and attitudes during the interview sessions. The informant, who has a characteristic of being courageous, was given the name Ares, while Athena was ascribed to the informant who were beautiful, lovely and well-versed on her field, Hera was attributed to the informant, who possess leadership skills on her grade level and serves as their queen of department. Rhea was given to the informant, who was a mother figure of their grade level and knowledgeable of good living as she was also a pastor, while the informant, who was good in music and like poems was named Apollo. Zeus was the name given to the informant who was a leader and king like of their department.

In the same manner, the eight participants were also given a pseudonym. They were Cronus, Themis, Poseidon, Hermes, Aphrodite, Persephone, Mnemosyne and Artemis. The name Cronus was given to the informant who was in long years in service and oldest among them was ascribed to the informant who showed timely in answering the questions, while Themis was attributed to the participant who has an expertise in values education, fair and justice and firm with her answers. The name Poseidon was given to the participant who has a fan of going in the beaches and love visiting different bodies of water. Hermes was ascribed to the participant who was a DJ and has an attribute of good voice in broadcasting was name given to the participant who was powerful voice during the interview, while the name Aphrodite was given to the participant who has a physical attribute of being lovely and beautiful. Persephone was the given name to the participant whose hobby is to plant vegetables and flowers. While the participant who was spontaneous in answering questions during interview was named Mnemosyne as she has a good memory in sharing her experiences.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>Code</i>
Ares	32	Male	Doctorate Degree	10	IDI-01
Athena	35	Female	Master's Degree	10	IDI-02
Hera	38	Female	Master's Degree	15	IDI-03
Rhea	45	Female	Bachelor's Degree	14	IDI-04
Apollo	51	Male	Bachelor's Degree	13	IDI-05
Zeus	44	Male	Master's Degree	15	IDI-06
Cronus	53	Male	Bachelor's Degree	15	IDI-07
Themis	42	Female	Master's Degree	12	IDI-08
Poseidon	40	Male	Master's Degree	15	IDI-09
Hermes	32	Male	Master's Degree	10	IDI-10
Aphrodite	35	Female	Master's Degree	12	IDI-11
Persephone	43	Female	Bachelor's Degree	12	IDI-12
Mnemosyne	49	Female	Bachelor's Degree	11	IDI-13
Artemis	44	Female	Bachelor's Degree	14	IDI-14
Total = 14					

Lastly, Artemis was the given name to the participant who was a characteristic of being very lovable to animals like dogs and cats. Both groups answered the same set of questions. The participants were selected based on the set criteria stated in the previous chapter of this study. The interview sessions that the researcher had with the participants manifested the composition of the sumptuous information included in this study.

The in-depth interview was performed and conducted in face-to-face manner which were the researcher came to the respective classroom and office of her participants individually at Sagayan National High School. The researcher used a mobile phone to record the data given by the participants. Recording data is a significant factor to consider in achieving and ensuring the validity and credibility of the study.

Categorization of Data

After completing extensive interviews, the audio tape was transcribed, translated, and examined. The analysis started with the coding procedure. Coding was the process of structuring things into text segments before giving the information meaning. The coding procedure was utilized to describe the people’s situations and categorize the topics for study. These concepts were utilized to develop a general description of the phenomenon under investigation. The data results were shown in the form of a table. The data acquired was given to the data analyst, who analyzed it and identified emergent patterns.

To categorize this data, the themes were presented according to the study questions and referred to as the major themes. The issues that emerged from the study were thoroughly examined, resulting in a lively discussion. The essential ideas of the participants’ responses were shown adjacent to the table’s major themes

The second step was data analysis, as seen in Table 2. To categorize this data, the topics were organized by research question and referred to as central themes. The table’s opposite important themes were the co-ideas generated by the participants’ comments. Another column was added to the table to represent the frequency of replies, which served as the foundation for the classification of general, typical, and variation as previously stated.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of secondary teachers in imposing discipline in light of the child protection policy?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview that was conducted with the respondents, respectively, hence, several sub questions were asked.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, six major themes emerged: supporting the implementation of the child protection policy, sustaining a consistent approach to discipline, creating a safe and conducive learning environment, arising probable misconceptions or misinterpretation of the policy, facing parental resistance and lack of support and balancing discipline with student’s well-being.

Table 2. The Experiences of Secondary Teachers in Imposing Classroom Discipline in Light of Child Protection Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Supporting the Implementation of the Child Protection Policy	“I feel like the child protection policy is necessary in ensuring the safety and welfare of our students.” – IDI01 “There’s a feeling of security and a safe learning environment of a child against any forms of abuses.” – IDI07 “I feel child protection policy is important for the welfare of our students and create environment where they feel comfortable and safe against all forms of abuses.” – IDI-12 “Child protection policy is somewhat implemented to protect children against all forms of abuse. There is a place for them called home that they are protected, accepted, appreciated and valued. And this policy served as their shield against abusive individuals.” – IDI-14
Sustaining a Consistent Approach to Discipline	“Notable struggles that I have encountered in imposing discipline includes maintaining consistency, managing resistance and balancing order while fostering a positive atmosphere amidst chaos.” – IDI-02 Lack of consistency, consistency is the key when it comes to discipline. If rules and consequences are not consistently enforced, students may not take them seriously. Also, lack of support, teachers face challenges in enforcing discipline if the lack support from school administration, parents or the community. Another thing is that understanding the root-cause and balancing discipline and positive reinforcement.” – IDI-09 “Having hard-headed students. There were times my patience is over knowing that I am only one. Therefore, I really struggle when in terms of disciplining my students from time-to-time you will remind them.” – IDI-13 “The notable struggles I have encountered is maintaining the discipline all the time. Sometimes, I tend to forget the discipline I impose because of their wrong behavior especially during discussion.” – IDI-14
Creating a Safe and Conducive Learning Environment	“Teachers will be mindful of their actions.” – IDI-03 “The advantage of CPP in imposing classroom discipline is the reinforcement of positive discipline which give way to all teachers in treating children as their own child.” – IDI-08 “Advantages of imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy include creating safe and conducive learning environment for all students, promoting respect and responsibility among students, and parenting disruptive behavior that may harm others. By setting clear expectations and consequences, teachers can help maintain order and ensure the well-being of all students.” -IDI-09 “We are guided and mindful to every action and decision to take part of it.” – IDI-13
Arising Probable Misconceptions or Misinterpretation of the Policy	“Students will tend to act inappropriately since they knew that they are protected with CPP.” – IDI-03 “For disadvantages, teachers cannot do drastic action when a child committed school instructions.” – IDI-07 “If there is a disadvantage is due to misconception and not fully understood by DepEd order.” – IDI- 08 “The disadvantage of this is may students will use it against to teachers and do disrespectful doings.” IDI-11 “Students are getting worst; they knew we can’t force them to follow us.” – IDI- 13
Facing Parental Resistance and Lack of Support	“So far, facing parents doesn’t know how to accept the truth. Parents spoiling children misbehavior.” IDI-06 “One of the most difficulty in imposing discipline to student is when parents consented their child to do school instructions.” – IDI-07 “When I tend to discipline my students because I want them to be a better person. But there are some parents who are consented their child. My intention is to discipline and not the other way around but they find it as a

	negative one.” – IDI-12
	“When the parents or guardian of that particular student is not aware of the behavior of their child and they think I am not doing it for their child’s good and for them it’s negative.” – IDI-13
Balancing Discipline with Student Well-Being	“Safety, fairness, clear communication and confidentiality.” – IDI-02
	“By imposing classroom reminds instead of classroom rules and regulations.” – IDI-03
	“Discipline should be positive. Discipline should encourage children to become good people and discipline should bring out the best in children due to reinforcement.” – IDI-08
	“Establish clear rules and being mindful about your student’s vulnerabilities.” – IDI-11
	“I considered the most is that my student’s good for their own beneficial. I impose rules where it is in favor to them but slightly, I still have a sense of authority for them to still be disciplined.” – IDI-12

Supporting the Implementation of the Child Protection Policy

Teachers have expressed strong support for the implementation of the Child Protection Policy by the Department of Education (DepEd), recognizing it as a vital measure to safeguard children from various forms of abuse. This policy establishes guidelines that create a secure environment for students, promoting their safety and well-being. The initiative is seen as a critical step in ensuring that educational institutions are places where children can thrive free from harm and exploitation.

Ares (pseudonym) stated that the implementation of the Child Protection Policy is necessary as it ensures the safety and welfare of the students. This policy is in favor of the students to protect them at all costs. Moreover, it establishes a framework that promotes a safe educational environment, free from violence, exploitation, and discrimination, thereby fostering students’ overall well-being. He stated that:

“I feel like the child protection policy is necessary in ensuring the safety and welfare of our students.” (IDI-01)

(I feel like the child protection policy is necessary in ensuring the safety and welfare of our students.)

Cronus (pseudonym) also shared that the Child Protection Policy is essential for the security of students and for fostering a safe learning environment. He emphasized that this policy not only safeguards students from harm but also creates a supportive atmosphere conducive to their educational growth. He stated that:

“There’s a feeling of security ug usa ka luwas nga palibot sa pagkat-on sa usa ka bata batok sa bisan unsang porma sa abuso.” (IDI-07)

(There’s a feeling of security and a safe learning environment of a child against any forms of abuses.)

Persephone (pseudonym) agreed with Cronus (pseudonym) that this policy plays an important role for the welfare of the students. It also creates a safe environment where students can be comfortable and free from all forms of abuse. This policy not only protects students but also fosters their emotional and social development, allowing them to thrive academically in a nurturing atmosphere. “She stated that:

“Para nako, importante ang child protection policy para sa kaayohan sa atong mga estudyante ug nagmugna kini og palibot diin sila makabati og kaharuhay ug seguridad batok sa tanan nga porma sa abuso.” (IDI-12)

(I feel child protection policy is important for the welfare of our students and create environment where they feel comfortable and safe against all forms of abuses.)

Artemis (pseudonym) expressed that the Child Protection Policy was implemented to protect children against abuses. This would serve as a shelter from abusive environments and provide a home where they are protected, appreciated, and valued. She emphasized that such a policy is crucial in empowering children to feel secure and supported, enabling them to flourish in their personal and academic lives. She stated that:

“Ang child protection policy kay gi-implementar aron protektahan ang mga bata batok sa tanan nga porma sa abuso. There is a place for them called home that they are protected, accepted, appreciated and valued. And this policy served as their shield against abusive individuals.” (IDI-14)

(Child protection policy is somewhat implemented to protect children against all forms of abuse. There is a place for them called home that they are protected, accepted, appreciated and valued. And this policy served as their shield against abusive individuals.)

Sustaining a Consistent Approach to Discipline

Secondary teachers stated that in imposing classroom discipline to students it should be consistent in order to establish smooth and ordered atmosphere inside the classroom. Although it is challenging but it must be consistent enough so that the students will take it seriously. They believe that consistency not only reinforces expectations but also helps build trust and respect between teachers and students, ultimately enhancing the learning experience.

Athena (pseudonym) seriously shared that maintaining consistency is one of her notable struggles in imposing discipline. As a teacher you have to manage and balance order so as to maintain a positive atmosphere within the classroom. Finding the right approach to

discipline requires ongoing reflection and adaptation, as each student has unique needs and responses that must be considered. She stated that:

“Notable struggles that I have encountered in imposing discipline...ahmm... apil na diraa ang pag... ahmm... maintaining consistency, managing resistance and balancing order while fostering a positive atmosphere amidst chaos.” (IDI-02)

(Notable struggles that I have encountered in imposing discipline includes maintaining consistency, managing resistance and balancing order while fostering a positive atmosphere amidst chaos.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) also expressed that consistency is the key to discipline. The rules and orders must be enforced consistently so that the students will take it seriously and also with the support of the school administration and stakeholders. He highlighted that a unified approach among educators and administrators is essential for fostering an environment where students understand the importance of discipline and accountability. He stated that:

“Notable struggles that I have encountered in imposing lack of consistency, consistency is the key when it comes to discipline. Kung ang mga rules ug mga consequences dili kanunay nga ipatuman, ang mga estudyante mahimong dili kini seryosohon. Usab, ang kakulang sa suporta naghatag og mga hagit sa mga magtutudlo sa pagpanghimatuud sa disiplina kung walay suporta gikan sa administrasyon sa eskwelahan, mga ginikanan, o sa komunidad. Another thing is that understanding the root-cause and balancing discipline and positive reinforcement.” (IDI-09)

(Notable struggles that I have encountered in imposing lack of consistency, consistency is the key when it comes to discipline. If rules and consequences are not consistently enforced, students may not take them seriously. Also, lack of support, teachers face challenges in enforcing discipline if the lack support from school administration, parents or the community. Another thing is that understanding the root-cause and balancing discipline and positive reinforcement.)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) honestly revealed that it is difficult to impose discipline inside the classroom especially when the students are hard-headed. From time-to-time, students should be reminded and patience is tested. She noted that effective discipline requires not only clear communication of expectations but also a compassionate approach that acknowledges the individual circumstances of each student. Ultimately, fostering a respectful and understanding environment can lead to better cooperation and improved behavior over time. She stated that:

“Having hard-headed students. Adunay mga higayon nga maubos ang akong pasensya knowing that I am only one. Therefore, naglisod gyud ko sa pagdisiplina sa akong mga estudyante kay gikan sa panahon ngadto sa panahon kinahanglan nimo silang pahimangnoan.” (IDI-13)

(Having hard-headed students. There were times my patience is over knowing that I am only one. Therefore, I really struggle when in terms of disciplining my students from time-to-time you will remind them.)

Artemis (pseudonym) also talked that maintaining discipline at all times is her notable struggle. She explained that the challenge lies in balancing authority with empathy, as students often test boundaries and require constant reinforcement of expectations. This ongoing effort demands her full attention and adaptability to ensure a respectful learning environment. Artemis stated that:

“We are guided and mindful to every action and decision to take part of it.” (IDI-13)

(Ahmm...we are guided and mindful to every action and decision to take part of it. Kana lang.)

Creating a Safe and Conducive Learning Environment

Teachers revealed that one of the advantages of child protection policy is to create a safe place for students and conducive learning environment. This policy helps students to feel comfortable and safe while learning. Learning becomes better when environment is secured and conducive. Moreover, a supportive atmosphere encourages active participation and engagement, allowing students to thrive academically and emotionally.

Hera (pseudonym) directly answered that through the implementation of child protection policy the teacher will be mindful to every action they will going to take. She emphasized that this heightened awareness fosters a culture of responsibility and care within the classroom, ensuring that all interactions prioritize the safety and well-being of students. As a result, teachers are better equipped to create a nurturing environment where students can learn and grow without fear. She stated that:

“Teachers will be mindful of their actions.” (IDI-03)

(Teachers will be mindful of their actions.)

Themis (pseudonym) discussed that the brighter side of this policy is to reinforce classroom discipline in such a good way or a positive one. And also, to treat students like their own child. By nurturing this relationship, teachers can create a supportive atmosphere that encourages students to respect the rules and engage more fully in their learning. Ultimately, this approach not only enhances discipline but also promotes emotional well-being among students. She stated that:

“The advantage of CPP in imposing classroom discipline is mao ang pagpalig-on sa positibong disiplina nga naghatag og kahigayunan sa tanan nga mga magtutudlo sa pagtreat sa mga bata sama sa ilang kaugalingong anak.” (IDI-08)

(The advantage of CPP in imposing classroom discipline is the reinforcement of positive discipline which give way to all teachers in treating children as their own child.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) also revealed that this policy creates a safe and conducive learning environment to students. And also, child protection policy mold individuals to be respectful and not to harm others. As teachers set rules and consequences, it helps students to maintain order and become better ones. He stated that:

“Advantages of imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy include creating safe and conducive learning environment para sa tanan nga estudyante, pagpalambo sa respeto ug responsibilidad taliwala sa mga estudyante, ug pagpugong sa makalilisan nga pamatasan nga mahimong makadaut sa uban. By setting clear expectations and consequences, teachers can help maintain order and ensure the well-being of all students.” (IDI-09)

(Advantages of imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy include creating safe and conducive learning environment for all students, promoting respect and responsibility among students, and parenting disruptive behavior that may harm others. By setting clear expectations and consequences, teachers can help maintain order and ensure the well-being of all students.)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) clearly stated that they were be all guided to every action they will going to take as this policy implemented. This guidance will ensure that all decisions align with the principles of respect and responsibility, fostering a positive environment for learning. Moreover, by adhering to these guidelines, students can contribute to a safe and supportive community where everyone thrives. She stated that:

“We are guided and mindful to every action and decision to take part of it.” (IDI-13)

(We are guided and mindful to every action and decision to take part of it.)

Arising Probable Misconceptions or Misinterpretation of the Policy

Teachers discussed that some of the students and their parents misinterpret the essence of implementation of child protection policy. They think that this policy was implemented to protect them at all cost. Students portrays misbehavior and then think that it still covers them up in doing things they wanted to do even if it crosses the limits. This misunderstanding can lead to a disregard for the boundaries set by the policy, ultimately undermining its purpose and effectiveness.

Hera (pseudonym) shared that student are acting inappropriately, as they rely on the policy, using it as a shield to cover up their misbehavior. This reliance not only distorts their understanding of the policy’s true intent but also fosters an environment where accountability is diminished, leading to further misconduct. Consequently, it is crucial to clarify the purpose of the child protection policy to ensure that students recognize the importance of responsible behavior and mutual respect. She stated that:

“Ang mga estudyante maghimo og dili angay nga mga aksyon tungod kay nahibalo sila nga sila giprotektahan sa CPP.” (IDI-03)

(Students will tend to act inappropriately since they knew that they are protected with CPP.)

Cronus (pseudonym) also shared that when students engage in wrongdoing or act inappropriately, teachers often feel unable to impose drastic measures or punishments. This limitation can create a challenging environment for educators, as it may lead to a perception of leniency that undermines the authority of the classroom. Consequently, it is essential to find a balance between protecting students and maintaining discipline to foster a respectful and productive learning atmosphere. He stated that:

“For disadvantages, teachers cannot do drastic action when a child committed school instructions.” (IDI-07)

(For disadvantages, teachers cannot do drastic action when a child committed school instructions.)

Themis (pseudonym) directly stated that there were misunderstanding or misconception of the DepEd order. This confusion often leads to misinterpretations of the guidelines, which can hinder effective implementation and create challenges for both educators and students. Furthermore, clarifying the intent and specifics of the order is essential to ensure that all stakeholders are aligned and can work together towards a common goal. She stated that:

“If there is a disadvantage is due to misconception and not fully understood by DepEd order.” (IDI-08)

(If there is a disadvantage is due to misconception and not fully understood by DepEd order.)

Aphrodite (pseudonym) expressed that because of this policy the students will use it against to the teachers where they would do disrespectful manners or doings. This misuse of the policy not only undermines the authority of educators but also creates a disruptive learning environment that affects all students. She stated that:

“The disadvantage of this is students will use it against to teachers and do disrespectful doings.” (IDI-11)

(The disadvantage of this is students will use it against to teachers and do disrespectful doings.)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) uncovered that the situation with the students is getting worse, and as teachers, they feel powerless to force students to comply with their expectations. This growing sense of frustration highlights the need for effective strategies to reestablish authority and encourage positive behavior in the classroom. She stated that:

“Students are getting worst; they knew we can’t force them to follow us.” (IDI-13)

(Students are getting worst; they knew we can’t force them to follow us.)

Facing Parental Resistance and Lack of Support

Teachers verbalize that the most difficult challenges they encounter in imposing child protection policy is where parents are lack of support and failed to understand the policy. They consented the behavior of their child. And also, some parents are not considering their child’s attitude and rather sees the disciplinary actions as a negative one.

Zeus (pseudonym) exposed that parents are spoiling their children without considering the truth, failing to tolerate their child’s misbehavior. This lack of accountability allows children to develop a sense of entitlement, believing they can act without consequences. As a result, the children may engage in increasingly inappropriate behavior, undermining their respect for authority and the values instilled by their educators. He stated that:

“So far, facing parents doesn’t know how to accept the truth. Ang mga ginikanan nagpasagdan ang dili maayo nga pamatasan sa ilang mga anak.” (IDI-06)

(So far, facing parents doesn’t know how to accept the truth. Parents spoiling children misbehavior.)

Cronus (pseudonym) also shared that one of the difficulties he encountered in imposing child protection policy is when the parents consented the actions or consented their child in doing the school instructions which sometimes created challenges in prioritizing the children’s safety and well-being over parental consent. He stated that:

“One of the most difficulty in imposing discipline para sa mga studyante kay kanang when parents consented their child to do school instructions.” (IDI-07)

(One of the most difficulty in imposing discipline to student is when parents consented their child to do school instructions.)

Persephone (pseudonym) agreed with Cronus (pseudonym) that it is difficult to discipline students even you are teaching them to become a better person. At some point, there were parents consented their child even if the intention is good and for the sake of their child. But for them it is negative. She stated that:

“When I tend to discipline sa akoang mga studyante kay gusto nako sila na mahimong better person. Pero naay mga parents na konsintihon ilahang mga anak. My intention is to discipline and not the other way around but they find it as a negative one.” (IDI-12)

(When I tend to discipline my students because I want them to be a better person. But there are some parents who are consented their child. My intention is to discipline and not the other way around but they find it as a negative one.)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) unveiled that it is difficult to impose discipline even if it is for the good of the students because there were parents of some students that is not aware of the attitude of their children. And with that, they only see the negative one and not the other way around. She stated that:

“When the parents or guardian sa kana na studyante kay dili aware sa behavior sa ilahang anak and they think I am not doing it for their child’s good and for them it’s negative.” (IDI-13)

(When the parents or guardian of that particular student is not aware of the behavior of their child and they think I am not doing it for their child’s good and for them it’s negative.)

Balancing Discipline with Student Well-Being

Teachers expressed that establishing a healthy and productive learning environment requires striking a balance between discipline and students’ well-being. Boundaries and structure are provided by discipline, while students are made to feel understood, supported, and valued by empathy. Students who receive positive discipline learn the skills necessary for leading balanced lives. Additionally, it enhances the rapport between students and teachers and fosters students’ sense of self-worth and contentment.

Athena (pseudonym) shared that it should be fair, safe and build clear communication and as well as confidentiality. This approach not only protects individuals but also builds trust within the community, encouraging open dialogue and collaboration. She stated that:

“Safety, fairness, clear communication and confidentiality.” (IDI-02)

(Safety, fairness, clear communication and confidentiality.)

Hera (pseudonym) stated that instead of imposing classroom discipline she made use of classroom reminders. In line with this, it encouraged a more positive learning environment but also empowered students to take responsibility for their actions. Students may feel or has a negative thought in terms of rules and regulations that is why through the term and way of reminders it can be a good effect to them. She stated that:

“By imposing classroom reminders instead of classroom rules and regulations.” (IDI-03)

(By imposing classroom reminders instead of classroom rules and regulations.)

Themis (pseudonym) also talked that discipline should be in a positive way and it could bring out the students best of them. By fostering an environment that encourages constructive behavior, educators can help students unlock their full potential and cultivate a sense of self-discipline that benefits their academic and personal growth. She stated that:

“Ang pagdisiplina dapat positive. Discipline should encourage children to become good people and discipline should bring out the best in children due to reinforcement.” (IDI-08)

Discipline should be positive. Discipline should encourage children to become good people and discipline should bring out the best in children due to reinforcement.” (IDI-08)

Aphrodite (pseudonym) revealed that you should knew your students’ vulnerabilities and established clear rules to create a supportive learning environment. By recognizing individual challenges and setting consistent expectations, educators can foster a sense of safety and belonging, enabling students to thrive academically and emotionally. She stated that:

“Establish clear rules and being mindful about your student’s vulnerabilities.” (IDI-11)

(Establish clear rules and being mindful about your student’s vulnerabilities.)

Persephone (pseudonym) uncover that she considers the students good and beneficial. And also impose discipline where more in favor of the students but there is still a sense of authority to let student’s follows. This is not only encourages students to thrive but also reinforces the importance of respect and accountability within the classroom. She stated that:

“I considered the most is that my student’s good for their own beneficial. I impose rules where it is in favor to them but slightly, I still have a sense of authority for them to still be disciplined.” (IDI-12)

(I considered the most is that my student’s good for their own beneficial. I impose rules where it is in favor to them but slightly, I still have a sense of authority for them to still be disciplined.)

Research Question No.2: How do secondary teachers cope up with the challenges in imposing classroom discipline in light of the child protection policy?

To answer this research question, an in-depth that was conducted with the respondents, respectively, hence, several sub questions were asked.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, five major themes emerged: exploring diverse resources for guidance, wisdom and support, adjusting with disciplinary methods to comply with the mandates of the child protection policy, implementing reinforcement and constructive feedback, staying calm and composed, and seeking assistance and guidance from colleagues.

Table 3. The Coping Mechanism of Secondary Teachers in Imposing Classroom Discipline in Light of Child Protection Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Exploring Diverse Resources for Guidance, Wisdom and Support	“I sought the advice of my colleagues and school principal on the implementation of this policy.” – IDI-01 “I asked the guidance counselor in our school on the child protection policy so I could adjust my dealings with my students.” – IDI-04 “Every time encountering challenges in imposing discipline, I run always reading my knowledge in adolescent psychology to understand their different uniqueness and status of living.” – IDI-05 “Attend trainings or seminar to stay informed about child protection policies and also building positive relationships with parent’s students and colleagues to create a supportive and collaborative environment that promotes open communication and trust. Another thing is that seeking support and guidance from school administrator’s counselors and other professionals when facing disciplinary situations.” – IDI-09
Adjusting with Disciplinary Methods to Comply with The Mandates of the Child Protection Policy	“I had to adjust my way of disciplining the students to adhere to the mandates of the CPP.” – IDI-01 “I am a kind of teacher who don’t speak bad words or fun of curses, so I guess making adjustments was not really a big deal with me.” – IDI-04 “Personal adjustment, being relaxed and calm. No law protecting teachers and as a teacher we should be aware of it.” – IDI-06 “Adjustments... so hinay-hinay no, hinay-hinay imohang gina-internalize ang mga orders, kay naa man gyuy mga order dinha nga... conflict sa imohang... kumbaga namat-an before. So therefore, e-review unya tapos imohang e-internalize unsa tong mga pros and cons about ato. So, para at least dili na ka mag lisod ug impose ani. So, sauna mag lisod gyud

	<p>ko ana pag-abot nako dinhi kay ... mao lagy ng nag dako ta sa mga kamot sa disciplinarian mao ng pag-abot dinhi is naay CPP. Unya naay mga butang nga dili diay to siya poyde under CPP. So mao to siya.” – IDI-10</p> <p>(“Adjustments...so slowly, you will slowly internalize the orders, because there were orders there that...conflict to your...I mean your practices before. So therefore, review and then you internalize what are the pros and cons about that. So at least you are not struggling or having hard times in imposing it. Therefore, before I really having difficulties when I arrived here...because I was raised in the hands of disciplinarian so when I arrived here there is CPP. And then there are things that is not right or allowed under CPP. So that is all.”)</p> <p>“I am adjusting myself the way I tolerate them, making them realized to their unnecessary actions and have an ample if patience.” – IDI-13</p>
Implementing Reinforcement and Constructive Feedback	<p>“Positive reinforcement established clear expectation, active listening and self-care.” – IDI-02</p> <p>“Positive discipline through one-on-one teacher and student conference with anecdotal records.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“Through a positive discipline and by adjusting myself so that students could meet in a half way.” – IDI-05</p> <p>“Use positive reinforcement acknowledge and reward positive behavior to encourage students to make good choices. Positive reinforcement can be a powerful tool in shaping behavior and promoting a supportive classroom environment.” – IDI-09</p> <p>“Through constructive feedback and positive reinforcement as well as prioritizing my mental health.” – IDI-14</p>
Staying Calm and Composed	<p>“I just remind myself that peace of mind matters most so I don’t actually take things seriously. I also walk my talk whatever is agreed will be followed.” – IDI-02</p> <p>“Do not cultivate your extreme emotions towards and keep calm always in all situation.” – IDI-07</p> <p>“One approach to managing personal sentiments and concerns is to maintain a professional demeanor and focus on the best interest of the students. It can be helpful to seek support from colleague’s mentors or school counsellors to process any emotional reactions and ensure that disciplinary actions are fair and appropriate.” – IDI-09</p> <p>“I will just keep myself at peace and calm, avoiding actions that would lead to discord while imposing discipline.” – IDI-11</p>
Seeking Assistance and Guidance from Colleagues	<p>“I sought the help of my colleagues and our grade head and principal whenever I encounter difficulties.” – IDI-01</p> <p>“Colleagues, such as the guidance counselor, prefect of discipline and principal.” – IDI-03</p> <p>“School administrators were providing advice on handling disciplinary issues within that framework of child protection policies. And also, colleagues and mentors whose experience teachers or mentors within the school community can offer insights strategies and support in dealing with challenging disciplinary situations while upholding child protection policies.” – IDI-09</p> <p>Colleagues and other person who’s higher or lengthy of service as a teacher than me.” – IDI-13</p>

Exploring Diverse Resources for Guidance, Wisdom and Support

Teachers uncovered that in support of the implementation of child protection policy in schools, provide comprehensive training and capacity building for school personnel to ensure they have a deep understanding of the policy’s provisions and their roles. And seek advice from colleagues.

Ares (pseudonym) verbalized that as this policy was implemented, he sought advice from respective colleagues and personnel. He emphasized the importance of collaboration during this process, noting that diverse perspectives helped refine the policy. Additionally, he expressed gratitude for the support he received, which contributed to a more effective implementation strategy. He stated that:

“I sought the advice of my colleagues and school principal on the implementation of this policy.” (IDI-01)

(I sought the advice of my colleagues and school principal on the implementation of this policy.)

Rhea (pseudonym) agreed Ares (pseudonym) that she also sought advice and guidance counselor and also adjusts herself in dealing with students. She recognized the necessity of adapting her approach to better meet the diverse needs of her students, fostering a supportive learning environment. She stated that:

“Mangutana ra ko sa guidance counselor sa school on the child protection policy para maka adjust ko sa pag deal sa akong mga studyante” (IDI-04)

(I asked the guidance counselor in our school on the child protection policy so I could adjust my dealings with my students.)

Apollo (pseudonym) also stated that he runs into reading his knowledge in adult psychology to understand the students. He believes that this knowledge is crucial for fostering better relationships and addressing the unique challenges faced by students. Furthermore, Apollo noted that staying informed about psychological principles enables him to implement effective strategies tailored to their needs. He stated that:

“Every time encountering challenges in imposing discipline, I run always reading my knowledge in adolescent psychology to understand their different uniqueness and status of living.” (IDI-05)

(Every time encountering challenges in imposing discipline, I run always reading my knowledge in adolescent psychology to understand their different uniqueness and status of living.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) said that attending trainings and seminar are good ways in understanding the implementation of child protection policy. With that, it builds good relationship in support and collaboration among students, parents and colleagues. He stated that:

“Mang-attend og mga training o seminar aron magpabilang updated bahin sa mga polisiya sa proteksyon sa bata and also building positive relationships sa mga ginikanan, studyante and colleagues to create a supportive and collaborative environment that promotes open communication and trust. Another thing is that seeking support and guidance from school administrator’s counselors and other professionals when facing disciplinary situations.” (IDI-09)

(Attend trainings or seminar to stay informed about child protection policies and also building positive relationships with parents’ students and colleagues to create a supportive and collaborative environment that promotes open communication and trust. Another thing is that seeking support and guidance from school administrator’s counselors and other professionals when facing disciplinary situations.)

Adjusting with Disciplinary Methods to Comply with the Mandates of the Child Protection Policy

Teachers said that they are adjusting disciplinary actions so as the students will follow and also for them not to feel stress and cross their limits. As to discipline students it should be in a positive approach that aligns with the policy. Also, by setting clear expectations, reinforcing positive behaviors and using non-physical consequences for misbehavior.

Ares (pseudonym) clearly answered that he adjusts his way of disciplining students just to abide the child protection policy. He understands that maintaining a safe and supportive environment is essential for student development. By adapting his disciplinary methods, Ares aims to foster trust and respect among his students while ensuring compliance with the policy. He stated that:

“Kinahaglan nko mag-adjust the way ko mag disiplin sa akoang mga studyante to adhere to the mandates of the CPP.” (IDI-01)

(I had to adjust my way of disciplining the students to adhere to the mandates of the CPP.)

Rhea (pseudonym) also shared that to avoid further conflict she just made simple reminders as she is a kind teacher who don’t utter bad words. She believes that positive reinforcement and gentle reminders create a more harmonious classroom atmosphere, allowing students to feel respected and valued. By maintaining this approach, Rhea fosters an environment where students are more receptive to guidance and support. She stated that:

“I am a kind of teacher who don’t speak bad words or fun of curses, so I guess making adjustments was not really a big deal with me.” (IDI-04)

(I am a kind of teacher who don’t speak bad words or fun of curses, so I guess making adjustments was not really a big deal with me.)

Zeus (pseudonym) revealed that adjusting his self and staying calm was his way of adjustment in dealing with difficulties in this policy. And also, being aware of the fact that there were no law protecting them. He expressed that this realization added to the challenges they faced, making it crucial to develop personal coping strategies amidst the uncertainty. He stated that:

“Kuan lang personal na pag adjust, being relaxed and calm. Walay balaod nga nag protekta sa mga teachers and as a teacher we should be aware of it.” (IDI-06)

(Personal adjustment, being relaxed and calm. No law protecting teachers and as a teacher we should be aware of it.)

Hermes (pseudonym) expressed that slowly adjustment was his way to understand the policy. In addition, he reviews what are the good side and bad and internalized the way it should be. He believes that this reflective process allows him to navigate the complexities of the policy more effectively. He stated that:

“Adjustments... so hinay-hinay no, hinay-hinay imohang gina-internalize ang mga orders, kay naa man gyuy mga order dinha nga... conflict sa imohang... kumbaga namat-an before. So therefore, e-review unya tapos imohang e-internalize unsa tong mga pros and cons about ato. So, para at least dili na ka mag lisod ug impose ani. So, sauna mag lisod gyud ko ana pag-abot nako dinhi kay ... mao lagy ng nag dako ta sa mga kamot sa disciplinarian mao ng pag-abot dinhi is naay CPP. Unya naay mga butang nga dili diay to siya poyde under CPP. So mao to siya.” (IDI-10)

(Adjustments...so slowly, you will slowly internalize the orders, because there were orders there that...conflict to your...I mean your practices before. So therefore, review and then you internalize what are the pros and cons about that. So at least you are not struggling or having hard times in imposing it. Therefore, before I really having difficulties when I arrived here...because I was raised in the hands of disciplinarian so when I arrived here there is CPP. And then there are things that is not right or allowed under CPP. So that is all.)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) also talked that in a way of adjusting herself to tolerate them and extend ample of patience was she made to adjust difficulties with the policy implanted. She emphasized that it does not only helped her cope but also fostered a deeper understanding of the complexities involved. She stated that:

“Nag adjust ko sa akoang kaugalingon the way I tolerate them, making them realized to their unnecessary actions and have an ample

of patience.” (IDI-13)

(I am adjusting myself the way I tolerate them, making them realized to their unnecessary actions and have an ample of patience.)

Implementing Reinforcement and Constructive Feedback

Teachers stated that their strategies in dealing with the difficult situations in having discipline with the students were through a positive discipline in which it couldn't harm students. Furthermore, acknowledge their good performance through a constructive feedback and give rewards to that individual who displays good attitude and shows kindness.

Athena (pseudonym) revealed that she deals it with positive reinforcement as it established a clear expectation. She believes that this method not only motivates herself but also encourages those around her to strive for improvement and adaptability in the face of policy changes. She stated that:

“Positive reinforcement established clear expectation, active listening and self-care.” (IDI-02)

(Positive reinforcement established clear expectation, active listening and self-care.)

Hera (pseudonym) agreed with Athena, (pseudonym) that through a positive discipline was her strategy in dealing with the difficulties in disciplining students and also setting a one-on-one conference to provide personalized support and foster deeper connections with students, enhancing their understanding and compliance in the learning environment. She stated that:

“Positive discipline through one-on-one teacher and student conference with anecdotal records.” (IDI-03)

(Positive discipline through one-on-one teacher and student conference with anecdotal records.)

Apollo (pseudonym) stated that by adjusting his self for students could be able to meet in a half-way and positive discipline was his strategy. Furthermore, he focuses on teaching rather than punishing, fostering a supportive environment where students can learn from their actions and develop essential social skills. He stated that:

“Through a positive discipline and by adjusting myself so that students could meet in a half way.” (IDI-05)

(Through a positive discipline and by adjusting myself so that students could meet in a half way.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) shared that using a positive reinforcement to acknowledge students and by giving rewards to those who displays good behavior so as to encourage students to make good choices. And also, through a positive reinforcement it shapes behavior and promotes classroom environment. He stated that:

“Use positive reinforcement acknowledge and reward positive behavior para ma encourage ang mga studyante na pilion ang sakto. Positive reinforcement can be a powerful tool in shaping behavior and promoting a supportive classroom environment.” (IDI-09)

(Use positive reinforcement acknowledge and reward positive behavior to encourage students to make good choices. Positive reinforcement can be a powerful tool in shaping behavior and promoting a supportive classroom environment.)

Artemis (pseudonym) also agreed with Apollo, (pseudonym) that his strategies was through a constructive feedback and positive reinforcement. She emphasized that providing specific, actionable feedback helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement, fostering a culture of growth and motivation in the learning environment. She stated that:

“Through constructive feedback and positive reinforcement as well as prioritizing my mental health.” (IDI-14)

(Through constructive feedback and positive reinforcement as well as prioritizing my mental health.)

Staying Calm and Composed

Teachers shared that in dealing with their personal sentiments and concerns with regards to the implementation of child protection policy they just stay in focus and calm. Also, dealt it with open mind and constant peace of mind. With that, being able to control emotions, maintain professional demeanor, and paying attention to the interest of the students.

Athena (pseudonym) talked that by reminding herself that peace of mind matters most and not taking too serious with the things that could lead to circumstances. Peace of mind is an essential quality for teachers, enabling them to navigate the challenges of the classroom while fostering a supportive learning environment. She stated that:

“I just remind myself that peace of mind matters most so mao to dli lang nako gina take ug seryuso ang mga butang. I also walk my talk whatever is agreed will be followed.” (IDI -02)

(I just remind myself that peace of mind matters most so I don't actually take things seriously. I also walk my talk whatever is agreed will be followed.)

Cronus (pseudonym) revealed that his way of dealing personal sentiments is that by not cultivating extreme emotions instead of being calm at all times. Also, it is important to teachers in maintaining a calm demeanor, as students benefit from educators who regulate

their own stress and foster a tranquil classroom environment. By embodying calmness, he not only enhances his own emotional well-being but also creates a supportive atmosphere for his students, allowing them to thrive amidst challenges. He stated that:

“Do not cultivate your extreme emotions towards and keep calm always in all situation.” (IDI-07)

(Do not cultivate your extreme emotions towards and keep calm always in all situation.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) discussed that to manage personal sentiments and concerns is to maintain professionalism and focus on the best interest of the students. Also, seeks support to the colleagues and authorized personnel that would address the needs to balanced fairness and appropriateness. He stated that:

“One approach to managing personal sentiments and concerns is kanang e-maintain lang ang professional demeanor and focus on the best interest of the students. It can be helpful to seek support from colleague’s mentors or school counsellors to process any emotional reactions and ensure that disciplinary actions are fair and appropriate.” (IDI-09)

(One approach to managing personal sentiments and concerns is to maintain a professional demeanor and focus on the best interest of the students. It can be helpful to seek support from colleague’s mentors or school counsellors to process any emotional reactions and ensure that disciplinary actions are fair and appropriate.)

Aphrodite (pseudonym) shared that she will just keep herself at peace and calm to avoid any discords. By prioritizing her inner tranquility, she believes she can effectively navigate conflicts and foster harmonious relationships, both personally and professionally. This commitment to maintaining a peaceful mindset not only benefits her own well-being but also sets a positive example for those around her, encouraging a culture of understanding and cooperation. She stated that:

“I will just keep myself at peace ug kalma rajud, iwasan ang mga actions that would lead to discord while imposing discipline.” (IDI-11)

(I will just keep myself at peace and calm, avoiding actions that would lead to discord while imposing discipline.)

Seeking Assistance and Guidance from Colleagues

Teachers unveiled that they sought help and assistance to their colleagues whenever they encountered difficult situations to handle as this policy being imposed. In addition, the school’s administrator, guidance counsellor and mentors who are higher in number of years in service.

Ares (pseudonym) stated that he sought help from his colleagues, grade head and their principal every time he needs. In addition, he is not only enhances his teaching practice but also fosters a supportive community within the school, where educators can share resources and strategies to improve student outcomes. By reaching out for assistance, Ares demonstrates the importance of teamwork in education, reinforcing that seeking help is a strength rather than a weakness. He stated that:

“Nangayo ko og tabang sa akong mga kauban, sa among grade head, ug sa principal kada magka-antos ko og kalisdanan.” (IDI-01)

(I sought the help of my colleagues and our grade head and principal whenever I encounter difficulties.)

Hera (pseudonym) also said that colleagues, principals, guidance counsellor and prefect of discipline where she asks for assistance if needed. This willingness to reach out for support underscores the importance of collaboration in the educational environment, as it fosters a network of resources that can help address challenges effectively. She stated that:

“Mga kauban, sama sa guidance counselor, prefect of discipline, ug principal.” (IDI-03)

(Colleagues, such as the guidance counselor, prefect of discipline and principal.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) shared that the school’s administrators provide advice in disciplinary issues. Furthermore, mentors and any other individual that can able to offer insights and strategies that could support in dealing with the challenging disciplinary situations. By leveraging the expertise of various school personnel, Poseidon enhances his ability to address disciplinary challenges while promoting a positive learning environment for all students. He stated that:

“Ang mga administrators sa skwelahan naghatag og tambag sa pagdumala sa mga isyu sa disiplina within that framework of child protection policies. And also, ang mga kauban ug mga mentor nga adunay kasinatian, mga magtutudlo o mentor sulod sa komunidad sa eskwelahan makahatag og mga panan-aw, estratehiya, ug suporta sa pag-atubang sa mga hagit nga sitwasyon sa disiplina samtang nagpadayon sa mga polisiya sa proteksyon sa bata.” (IDI-09)

“School administrators were providing advice on handling disciplinary issues within that framework of child protection policies. And also, colleagues and mentors whose experience teachers or mentors within the school community can offer insights strategies and support in dealing with challenging disciplinary situations while upholding child protection policies.” (IDI-09)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) agreed with Hera and Poseidon (pseudonym) that she also ask help and assistance to her colleagues and any other persons that years in service is lengthy. She believes that tapping into the wisdom and experience of seasoned educators not only

enriches her own practice but also fosters a collaborative spirit within the school community. She stated that:

Colleagues and other person who's higher or lengthy of service as a teacher than me." (IDI-13)

(Colleagues and other person who's higher or lengthy of service as a teacher than me.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights of secondary teachers in imposing discipline in light of the child protection policy?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview that was conducted with the respondents, respectively, hence, several sub questions were asked.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 were presented in Table 4. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: maintain an open-minded and positive attitude towards policy implementation, view the importance of parental communication in addressing student behavior, become adaptable in facing challenges and changes and, balance between protecting students and supporting teachers.

Table 4. The Insights of Secondary Teachers in Imposing Classroom Discipline in Light of Child Protection Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Maintain an Open-Minded and Positive Attitude Towards Policy Implementation	<p>"I would say to my co-teachers that they should be open-minded in relation to this implementation." – IDI-01</p> <p>"Whatever happens in the classroom never make it as a big deal. Just leave it there." – IDI-03</p> <p>"Always look at the brighter side of the purpose of this policy nga gi-implement. Kay nganong gi implement siya? Nganong kana nga policy ang gipili nganong giimplement sa school kay therefore naa man gyud na siyay reason nganong kana ang gi implement. That is why we need to understand, comprehend and rason nganong kana siya ag gi Kuan. And of course, I do believe para gyud na siya sa mga studyante." – IDI-10</p> <p>(Always look at Look at the brighter side of the purpose of this policy that was implemented. Why it is being implemented? Why that policy was chosen to be implemented in school because... therefore it has a reason why it is implemented. That is why we need to understand, comprehend and the reason why that was... and of course, I do believe that it is for the students.")</p> <p>"Be positive, be strong and continue the good practices. As a teacher it is our duty and responsibility to take good care of our students in school and impart our knowledge to them. Just embrace the reality of being a teacher." – IDI-12</p> <p>"Do not take personally on way happens in the classroom because in the end, we will put ourselves at risks." – IDI-14</p>
View the Importance of Parental Communication in Addressing Student Behavior	<p>"Communicate and ask help from parents. They know their child better than you." – IDI-02</p> <p>"Just be a good teacher, be a parent to erring students. They may have problems at home. Talk to their parents and educate them on how to best discipline and treat their children." – IDI-08</p> <p>"They must to observe the behavior of students and then if there's something, that is the time to call their attention in order for them to stop that behavior. If they still continue doing, call the attention of parents." – IDI-09</p> <p>"Communicate to your students well and also to their parents since they have the full power to discipline their child." – IDI-11</p>
Become Adaptable in Facing Challenges and Changes	<p>"It helped me to become more resilient and be more positive to certain changes." – IDI-01</p> <p>"It shaped me into a more resilient person and made me realize that myself matters most so choose how to handle things up." – IDI-02</p> <p>"It shaped as to become a better and more patient person." – IDI-03</p> <p>"It shaped me in a way that I become more resilient. Reality hits me so hard that during our time corporal punishments exists. But I am proud of it because we are well-disciplined. Unlike today, students are too much sensitive, as a result they're the one who threat teachers because they knew they are protected." – IDI-12</p>
Balance Between Protecting Students and Supporting Teachers	<p>"We live in a world where good and evil still exist. So when DepEd thought about this policy- they think of the evil and tend to protect the students. Causes are also being done in the court because of evil acts that very few teachers are involved. May the government re-consider the thought that education in the first place is good for good and always good. Discipline is also good to protect every child in our society." – IDI-04</p> <p>"Students were too much protected with the policy. I suggest to recall corporal discipline." – IDI-06</p> <p>"Take a look back on the implementation of CPP because there were some of it is not right. It is too much in terms of protection to children." – IDI-09</p> <p>"Review and evaluate some of it. I suggest that CPP should not be tighten. Although it is good but the reality, students are becoming too much confident and spoiled. And as a teacher, there is no such way to control them because not all the time their wants are good for them. There is no teacher who that will get mad to her/his students if the students portray good behavior." – IDI-12</p> <p>"They should also consider the side of the teachers. And also, before implementing a policy, it should be checked thoroughly on its different side so that it will not cause or create another problem to be face in the future." – IDI-13</p> <p>"They should also make a policy that can protect the teachers whenever students will disrespect their teachers and will commit unlawful actions." – IDI-14</p>

Maintain an Open-Minded and Positive Attitude Towards Policy Implementation

Teachers shared that for their co-teachers to feel good despite of the differences they encountered in imposing discipline in light of child protection policy is to maintain it and be open-minded. There were always be a good and bad comments. Also, recognize that

people have different perspectives, experiences and ways of thinking. View the brighter side of the purpose of this policy. Understanding, positivity, and management conquers all. Embracing the policy and be open to changes.

Ares (pseudonym) verbalized that the message he could give to his co-teachers is to be open-minded. He believes that an open-minded approach encourages the sharing of diverse ideas and perspectives, which can lead to more effective teaching strategies. By embracing new concepts and being receptive to feedback, educators can create a more dynamic and inclusive learning environment for their students. He stated that:

“I would say to my co-teachers that they should be open-minded in relation to this implementation.” (IDI-01)

(I would say to my co-teachers that they should be open-minded in relation to this implementation.)

Hera (pseudonym) honestly answered that never make it as a big deal whatever happens. She believes that maintaining a balanced perspective helps her navigate challenges more effectively, allowing her to focus on solutions rather than dwelling on problems. By adopting this mindset, she fosters a positive atmosphere in her classroom, encouraging her students to approach difficulties with resilience and composure. She stated that:

“Whatever happens in the classroom never make it as a big deal. Just leave it there.” (IDI-03)

(Whatever happens in the classroom never make it as a big deal. Just leave it there.)

Hermes (pseudonym) discussed that see the brighter side of the policy because there were reasons behind that policy. Understand and comprehend the reason why it is implemented. By doing so, he believes that educators can better appreciate the intention behind the policy and adapt their practices accordingly, ultimately benefiting both teachers and students in the learning environment. He stated that:

“Always look at the brighter side of the purpose of this policy nga gi-implement. Kay nganong gi implement siya? Nganong kana nga policy ang gipili nganong giimplement sa school kay therefore naa man gyud na siyay reason nganong kana ang gi implement. That is why we need to understand, comprehend and rason nganong kana siya ag gi Kuan. And of course, I do believe para gyud na siya sa mga studyante.” (IDI-10)

(Always look at look at the brighter side of the purpose of this policy that was implemented. Why it is being implemented? Why that policy was chosen to be implemented in school because... therefore it has a reason why it is implemented. That is why we need to understand, comprehend and the reason why that was... and of course, I do believe that it is for the students.)

Persephone (pseudonym) shared that being always positive, strong and continue doing good things or practices. Also, embrace the responsibility of a teacher for it is a duty to take good care of the students. By maintaining a positive outlook and demonstrating strength, Persephone believes that teachers can inspire their students to overcome challenges and foster a nurturing learning environment. She stated that:

“Be positive, be strong and continue the good practices. Isip mga magtutudlo, atong katungdanan ug responsibilidad ang pag-atiman sa atong mga estudyante sa eskwelahan ug paghatag sa atong kahibalo kanila. Dawata lang ang realidad sa pagka-magtutudlo.” (IDI-12)

(Be positive, be strong and continue the good practices. As a teacher it is our duty and responsibility to take good care of our students in school and impart our knowledge to them. Just embrace the reality of being a teacher.)

Artemis (pseudonym) also talked that do not put all things personally for maybe at the end they put themselves in a risk. She emphasized that by maintaining a broader perspective, individuals can protect themselves from the risks associated with overreacting to situations, allowing for healthier interactions and a more positive environment. She stated that:

“Dili lang nato siya e-take personally on way happens in the classroom because in the end, we will put ourselves at risks.” (IDI-14)

(Do not take personally on way happens in the classroom because in the end, we will put ourselves at risks.)

View Importance of Parental Communication in Addressing Student Behavior

Teachers discussed that it is important to parents to be aware of the status, performances, and behavior of their child in school. Furthermore, parent’s interventions are important as they are once who knows their child better. Open and ongoing communication allows teachers to inform parents about any behavioral concerns in the classrooms. Parents can reinforce the same expectations and consequences at home, helping the student understand that their behavior is important to both their family and school.

Athena (pseudonym) honestly stated that constant communication to parents and ask them for help with regards to the behavior of their child for they know better. She believes that by actively involving parents in the conversation, teachers can create a collaborative approach to addressing behavioral issues, ultimately fostering a more effective partnership in the child’s education. She stated that:

“Makigcommunicate ra ug mangayo ug tabang sa mga ginikanan. Mas naka ila na sila sa ilahang anak kaysa imoha.” (IDI-02)

(Communicate and ask help from parents. They know their child better than you.)

Themis, (pseudonym) directly answered that be a good teacher and understand students for they maybe experienced bad at home. Also, inform parents to be aware of their child's behavior at school. Additionally, she emphasized the importance of informing parents about their child's behavior at school, encouraging them to be proactive in addressing any issues and providing the necessary support for their child's well-being. Themis stated that:

“Magpaka-maayo lang nga magtutudlo, mahimong usa ka ginikanan sa mga estudyanteng nagkamali. Basin adunay sila mga problema sa balay. Istorya sa ilang mga ginikanan ug tudlui sila kung unsaon pagdisiplina ug pag-atiman sa ilang mga anak.” (IDI-08)

(Just be a good teacher, be a parent to erring students. They may have problems at home. Talk to their parents and educate them on how to best discipline and treat their children.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) clearly revealed that observing student's behavior must be the first thing to do and if there is wrong, then call the attention of parents. He emphasized that early intervention is crucial, as it allows for timely support and guidance, ensuring that students receive the help they need to improve their behavior. By fostering open communication with parents, educators can work together to address any underlying issues that may be affecting the student's performance and well-being. He stated that:

“Kinahanglan nilang obserbahan ang pamatasan sa mga estudyante ug kung adunay makita, kana na ang panahon aron tawagon ang ilang atensyon aron mapahunong ang maong pamatasan. Kung magpadayon gihapon sila, tawagi ang atensyon sa mga ginikanan.” (IDI-09)

(They must to observe the behavior of students and then if there's something, that is the time to call their attention in order for them to stop that behavior. If they still continue doing, call the attention of parents.)

Aphrodite (pseudonym) also revealed that constant communication to students and parents should be also consider. Furthermore, maintaining an open line of communication fosters a supportive environment, allowing for better understanding of students' needs and challenges. By engaging both students and their families, educators can create a collaborative approach that enhances the overall learning experience. She stated that:

“Maayo nga makig-communicate sa imong mga estudyante ug usab sa ilang mga ginikanan tungod kay sila adunay tibuok nga gahum sa pagdisiplina sa ilang anak.” (IDI-11)

(Communicate to your students well and also to their parents since they have the full power to discipline their child.)

Become Adaptable in Facing Challenges and Changes

Teachers stated that developing resilience is crucial for teachers for effectively navigate the challenges and demands of the profession. Resilient teachers are better equipped to manage stress, maintain their well-being, and sustain their effectiveness over the long term. Also, building teacher resilience benefits the entire school community. In addition, teacher resilient is an investment in the success of the whole community. Better able to create an engaging, supportive learning environments for their students. By cultivating these qualities, teachers can bounce back from setbacks, adapt to change, and maintain a positive, solutions-oriented attitude.

Ares (pseudonym) shared that it shaped him to become a resilient and being positive to certain changes. Also, embracing challenges has not only strengthened his character but also equipped him with the skills to adapt and thrive in dynamic environments, ultimately benefiting both his personal growth and his role as an educator. He stated that:

“It helped me to become more resilient and be more positive to certain changes.” (IDI-01)

(It helped me to become more resilient and be more positive to certain changes.)

Athena (pseudonym) expressed that it also shaped her into a resilient person. She noted that developing resilience has allowed her to face challenges with confidence and adaptability, enabling her to grow both personally and professionally. By embracing the lessons learned from adversity, she believes she can inspire others to cultivate their own resilience in the face of difficulties. She stated that:

“Nakahimo kini kanako nga mahimong usa ka mas lig-on nga tawo ug nakapahibalo kanako nga ang akong kaugalingon ang labing importante, busa pili-a kung unsaon pag-atubang sa mga butang.” (IDI-02)

(It shaped me into a more resilient person and made me realize that myself matters most so choose how to handle things up.)

Hera (pseudonym) also said that it shaped her into a better person and extend patient. In addition, through her experiences, she has learned the value of empathy and understanding, which allows her to connect more deeply with her students and colleagues. By cultivating patience, she believes she can create a more supportive and nurturing environment for everyone around her. She stated that:

“It shaped as to become a better and more patient person.” (IDI-03)

(It shaped as to become a better and more patient person.)

Persephone (pseudonym) revealed that it shaped her into more resilient. However, reality speaks for his self that during his time there were corporal punishments unlike today it is not allowed. She reflected on how these past practices influenced her development and highlighted the importance of understanding the negative impacts of such disciplinary methods on students' well-being and behavior. She stated that:

“Nakahimo kini kanako nga mahimong mas lig-on. Ang realidad nakapahimulos kanako nga sa among panahon, adunay mga corporal punishments. Apan proud ko niini tungod kay maayo kami nga nadisiplinahan. Dili sama karon, ang mga estudyante sobra ka sensitibo, ug resulta niini, sila na ang naghulga sa mga magtutudlo tungod kay kabalo sila nga sila giprotektahan.” (IDI-12)

(It shaped me in a way that I become more resilient. Reality hits me so hard that during our time corporal punishments exists. But I am proud of it because we are well-disciplined. Unlike today, students are too much sensitive, as a result they're the one who threat teachers because they knew they are protected.)

Balance Between Protecting Students and Supporting Teachers

Teachers stated that there must be a balance struck between safeguarding pupils from any type of maltreatment at all costs. At the same time, support teachers in achieving common goals. Teachers wanted their students to develop self-discipline. Furthermore, kids have a fundamental right to feel protected, respected, and supported in their educational environment. Schools owe a duty of care to prevent and resolve bullying, harassment, discrimination, and abuse. Additionally, teachers play an important role in educating and nurturing pupils. They need to feel empowered, valued, and supported at work. Both schools can foster a healthy, productive, and safe environment for all students by providing support and empowerment.

Rhea (pseudonym) seriously stated that in a world we lived there good and evil still exist. There should be a reconsideration of the thought that education is good for students at all times. And also, discipline is good so as to protect children as it helps instill values and boundaries that are crucial for their development. She believes that while education is vital, it must be complemented by appropriate disciplinary measures to ensure a well-rounded upbringing for students. She stated that:

“We live in a world where good and evil still exist. So when DepEd thought about this policy- they think of the evil and tend to protect the students. Causes are also being done in the court because of evil acts that very few teachers are involved. Hinaut nga ang gobyerno mag-reconsider sa hunahuna nga ang edukasyon sa una kay maayo para sa maayo ug kanunay nga maayo. Ang disiplina usab maayo aron mapanalipdan ang matag bata sa atong katilingban. (IDI-04)

(We live in a world where good and evil still exist. So when DepEd thought about this policy- they think of the evil and tend to protect the students. Causes are also being done in the court because of evil acts that very few teachers are involved. May the government reconsider the thought that education in the first place is good for good and always good. Discipline is also good to protect every child in our society.)

Zeus (pseudonym) directly verbalized that there was too much protection to students. With that, he suggests corporal punishment. To add more, certain level of discipline is necessary to prepare students for the realities of life, arguing that without it, they may struggle to understand consequences and accountability. Zeus feels that while the intention behind protecting students is noble, it can lead to a lack of resilience and responsibility in their behavior. He stated that:

“Students were too much protected with the policy. I suggest to recall corporal discipline.” (IDI-06)

(Students were too much protected with the policy. I suggest to recall corporal discipline.)

Poseidon (pseudonym) clearly shared that looking back to the implementation of child protection policy for some is not right or aligned. He expressed concern that while the intention behind the policy is to safeguard students, it may inadvertently limit teachers' ability to address misbehavior effectively. Poseidon suggested that a balance must be struck to ensure both protection and discipline, allowing educators to maintain a conducive learning environment while still respecting students' rights. He stated that:

“Take a look back on the implementation of CPP because there were some of it is not right. It is too much in terms of protection to children.” (IDI-09)

(Take a look back on the implementation of CPP because there were some of it is not right. It is too much in terms of protection to children.)

Persephone (pseudonym) honestly expressed that reviewing and evaluating the policy is needed. In addition, this policy is good but the children are getting worst since they knew that there is protecting them. Also, current level of protection may lead to a sense of entitlement among students, making them less accountable for their actions. Persephone advocates for a balanced approach that combines protection with appropriate discipline to ensure that students understand the consequences of their behavior. She stated that:

“Usisaon ug e-evaluate ang uban niini. Sugyot nako nga ang CPP dili dapat ipugngan og maayo. Bisan pa man nga maayo kini, ang realidad mao nga ang mga estudyante nagkadako ang kumpiyansa ug nagpasagad. Ug ingon usa ka magtutudlo, walay paagi aron makontrol sila tungod kay dili sa tanan nga panahon ang ilang gusto maayo para kanila. Wala'y magtutudlo nga masuko sa iyang mga estudyante kung ang mga estudyante nagpakita og maayong pamatasan.” (IDI-12)

(Review and evaluate some of it. I suggest that CPP should not be tighten. Although it is good but the reality, students are becoming too much confident and spoiled. And as a teacher, there is no such way to control them because not all the time their wants are good for them. There is no teacher who that will get mad to her/his students if the students portray good behavior.)

Mnemosyne (pseudonym) also talked that there should also be a consideration to the side of the teachers. There should be a thorough checking and evaluation between both sides of policy before it is implemented to avoid further conflict. She emphasized that teachers' perspectives and experiences are crucial in shaping effective policies, as their involvement can lead to better understanding and smoother implementation. By ensuring that both teachers and students are considered in policy discussions, she believes that a more balanced and effective approach can be achieved, ultimately benefiting the educational environment. She stated that:

“Kinahanglan usab nilang ikonsiderar ang bahin sa mga magtutudlo. Ug usab, sa dili pa ipatuman ang usa ka polisiya, kinahanglan kini usisahon og maayo sa nagkalain-laing aspeto aron dili kini magdala o maghimo og lain pang problema nga atubangon sa umaabot.” (IDI-13)

(They should also consider the side of the teachers. And also, before implementing a policy, it should be checked thoroughly on its different side so that it will not cause or create another problem to be face in the future.)

Conclusions

The result of this phenomenal inquiry provides valuable insights into the perspectives of teachers with regards to imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy. The results of this research can be used to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences of teachers as well as the challenges they faced and the strategies they faced to cope with them. This information can be used to inform the educational system about how child protection policy affects student's behaviour and teachers in shaping students in a way of disciplining them for their own good.

As students, teachers, parents, school administrators, and mentors, we must gain as much as knowledge and understanding as possible about the experiences and challenges of the teachers in dealing with imposing classroom policy in light of child protection policy. By understanding the teachers, we can develop and implement strategies in order to cope up with the challenges they faced.

Furthermore, this study could help the teachers and administrators of the school as well as the parents to further understand and gain more knowledge on how to support the students as well as the teachers to become effective in the classroom management. School administrators could provide support by giving advice to teachers in dealing with diverse attitude and uniqueness of students, create program that would develop and support teachers in managing students in a difficult situations and shared strategies in dealing such difficulties in teaching that would abide the child protection policy. On the other hand, it could push the teachers to create a safe and conducive space environment for learning in order to help students establish clear understanding about the policy.

Additionally, the purpose of this study was to determine how the adoption of child protection policies affects teachers' perspectives in various ways. On the other hand, child protection policies have both beneficial and negative consequences for instructors. As a result, the findings of this study may assist them understand the value of having a well-disciplined student and practicing positive discipline. Teachers will be able to act in a way that children will follow for their own good while also not violating the law or causing harm to students.

Lastly, this may help teachers who had undergone and experienced enforcing classroom discipline in the presence of a child protection policy understand what the true purpose of having a child protection policy in place was. It is important to remember that teachers' viewpoints should be prioritized while developing and implementing regulations.

This study, which examined the perspectives of 14 teachers at Sagayan National High School, provided useful insights into teachers' experiences with imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policies. However, it is important to emphasize that the results of this qualitative study are limited to the experiences of these specific participants and may not be applicable to other groups or circumstances.

Therefore a result, additional research is required to repeat this study in multiple regions, with a bigger and more diverse sample size, and using qualitative and quantitative research methodologies to collect more detailed data. They are also looking into the viewpoints of elementary kids and instructors, who have valuable insights to give about implementing punishment in light of child protection policies. This will help to demonstrate the findings' validity and generalizability, as well as provide a more comprehensive knowledge of high school teachers and students' attitudes toward implementing classroom punishment in light of child protection policies.

Furthermore, future research should broaden the scope of the study by incorporating a bigger and more diverse sample size, as well as enrolling people from various regions and backgrounds. This will provide a more comprehensive grasp of high school teachers' perspectives on administering classroom discipline in the context of child protection policies. Future research will include a more diverse sample to investigate the potential impact of these demographic factors on high school teachers' implementing classroom discipline in light of child protection policies. In conclusion, while this study provided useful insights into high school teachers' experiences with imposing classroom discipline in light of child protection policy, more research is needed to replicate and expand on these findings in different contexts and with a larger and more diverse sample size.

References

- Aksoy, P. (2020). The challenging behaviors faced by the preschool teachers in their classrooms, and the strategies and discipline approaches used against these behaviors: the sample of United States. *Particip. Educ. Res.* 7, 79–104. Doi: 10.17275/per.20.36.7.3.
- Alfandari, R. (2017). Evaluation of a national reform in the Israeli child protection practice designed to improve children’s participation in decision-making. *Child & Family Social Work*, 22, 54–62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.12261>.
- Al-Qaysi, N. (2018). The impact of child protection policy on Omani classrooms. *International Journal of Information Technology and Language Studies*, 2(1), 1-11. <http://journals.sfu.ca/ijitl>
- American Psychological Association, Sexual abuse, 2021, <https://www.apa.org/topics/sexual-assault-harassment>.
- Ancho, I. (2019). Preferred future of Filipino leadership. No.1: 1-12. Retrieved on September 8, 2021 from <https://so05.tcithaijo.org/index.php/irdssru/article/view/145239>.
- Asio, J. M.R., Bayucca, S. A., & Jimenez, E. C. (2020). Child protection policy awareness of teachers and responsiveness of the school: Their relationship and implications. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 9(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v9i1.3384>
- Bayucca, Shallimar A. (2020). Teachers’ Awareness and School’s Responsiveness to the Child Protection Policy: Basis for a Development Plan. https://www.academia.edu/43479262/Teachers_Awareness_and_Schools_Responsiveness_to_the_Child_Protection_Policy_Basis_for_a_Development_Plan.
- Becker, S. A., Brown, M., Dahlstrom, E., Davis, A., DePaul, K., Diaz, V., & Pomerantz, J. (2018). CMN Horizon report: 2018 Higher education edition. Retrieved from <https://library.educause.edu/~media/files/library/2018/8/2018horizonreport.pdf>
- Canadian Mental Health Association (2021). Fast facts about mental health and mental illness. <https://cmha.ca/brochure/fast-facts-about-mental-illness/>
- Cassidy, J., & Shaver, P. R., (2018). *Handbook of attachment: Theory, research and clinical applications*, (3rd ed.). New York: Guilford.
- Castino, L. G. (2023). Child Protection Policy and Behavioral Management Practices at a Public Elementary School in Rizal, Philippines. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 4(1), 107-119. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.01.12>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Division of Violence Prevention (2019). <https://www.childwelfare.gov/topics/preventing/promoting/protectfactors/>
- Cervancia, J.M, Hernandez, K.U, Rodavia, M., Roxas,E. (2019). Child abuse and compliance on child protection policy in private and public basic educational institutions. *International Journal for Cross Disciplinary Subjects in Education*, 10, (1), 3957-3963.
- Child Welfare Information Gateway. (2020). How the child welfare system works. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, Children’s Bureau. <https://www.childwelfare.gov/bs/factsheets/cpswork/>
- Cho, V., Mansfield, K.C., Claughton, J. (2020). The past and future technology in classroom management and school discipline: A systematic review. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 90, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103037>
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* / John W. Creswell. — 4th ed.
- DepEd Order No. 40 series 2012. DepEd Child Protection Policy. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2012/05/DO_s2012_40.pdf.
- Duarte, B. J., and Brewer, C. A. (2019). “Caught in the nets of ‘discipline’”: understanding the possibilities for writing teachers’ resistance to standardization in local policy. *Educ. Policy* 33, 88–110. Doi: 10.1177/0895904818807326.
- Durrant, Joan E. (2020). Recognizing the child’s right to protection from physical violence: An update on progress and a call to action. Durrant JE, Stewart-Tufescu A, Afifi TO. Recognizing the child’s right to protection from physical violence: An update on progress and a call to action. *Child Abuse Negl.* 2020 Dec;110(Pt 1):104297. Doi: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2019.104297. Epub 2019 Nov 30. PMID: 31796214. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31796214/>.
- Dng, T. M., Nga, N. T., and Vu-Nhu, T. H. (2020). Teachers and STEM education: collaboration across disciplines and implementation of lessons in two subject areas. *Univ. J. Educ. Res.* 8, 4122–4128. Doi: 10.13189/ujer.2020.080938.
- Drake, Gabrielle, et al. (2019). “Is there a Place for Children as Emotional Beings in Child Protection Policy and Practice?” *International*

Journal of Emotional Education, vol. 11, no. 1, 2019,

Department of Social Welfare and Development. (2021a). Nationwide Directory of Private Social Welfare and Development Agencies (SWDAs) with VALID Registration, Registration and License/License to Operate and/or Accreditation issued by DSWD As of January 27, 2021. <https://caraga.dswd.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Private-SWDAs-with-valid-RLA-01272021.pdf>

Eremie, M.D., & Doueyi-Fiderikumo, J. (2018). Positive Reinforcement on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in River State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research* 6(2):48-56. [File://mtshscfs01/home\\$/iadam/Desktop/Summary/IJISSER-J-7-2018.pdf](File://mtshscfs01/home$/iadam/Desktop/Summary/IJISSER-J-7-2018.pdf)

Estremera, Michael L. (2018). "The Boons and Banes of Child Protection Policy: The Sorsogon West Landscape." *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2018, pp. 71-79.

Finkelhor, H. Turner, B. K. Wormuth, J. Vanderminden, and S. Hamby, (2020). "Corporal punishment: current rates from a national survey," *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, vol. 28, no. 7, pp. 1991-1997.

Furman, C. 2018. "Descriptive Inquiry: Cultivating Practical Wisdom with Teachers." *Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice* 24 (5): 559-570. [Doi:10.1080/13540602.2018.1452727](https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2018.1452727).

Fluke, John et al., (2010). UNICEF role in emergency, <http://www.unicef.org/emerge/files/childprotectionpolicy.pdf>.

Fry et al., (2017). Child protection and safeguarding in initial teacher education: A systematic scoping review. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0190740923001469> Fry et al., (2017). Child protection and safeguarding in initial teacher education: A systematic scoping review. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0190740923001469>

Fylkesnes, J. Taylor, A.C. Iversen (2018). Children's experiences with Child Protection Services: A synthesis of qualitative evidence. *Sciencedirect*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.104974>

Gershun M, Terrebonne C. (2018). Child welfare system interventions on behalf of children and families: Highlighting the role of court appointed special advocates. *Curr Probl Pediatr Adolesc Health Care*. Sep;48(9):215-231.

Harding, S., Morris, R., Gunnella, D., Ford, T., et al. (2019), Is teachers' mental health and wellbeing Associated with students' mental health and wellbeing? *Journal of Affective Disorders* 242 (2019) 180-187.

Hermino, Agustinus (2020). "Peace Education and Child Protection in Educational Settings for Elementary School in the West Papua of Indonesia." *Asian Social Science*, vol. 13, No. 8, pp. 20-31.

How Poor Parental Support Affects Student Growth and Achievement. (2019). Retrieved January 31, 2023 from [fedena.comhttps://www.researchgate.net/publication/369479747_Lack_of_Parental_Support_Unfavourable_in_Leading_to_Progression](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369479747_Lack_of_Parental_Support_Unfavourable_in_Leading_to_Progression)

Hu MH, Huang GS, Huang JL, Wu CT, Chao AS, Lo FS, Wu HP. (2018). Clinical characteristic and risk factors of recurrent sexual abuse and delayed reported sexual abuse in childhood. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. Apr; 97(14):e0236.

Hughes, M. A. Bellis, K. A. Hardcastle et al., (2017). "The effect of multiple adverse childhood experiences on health: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *The Lancet Public Health*, vol. 2, no. 8, pp. e356-e366.

Jackson, Kate (2017). <https://www.socialworktoday.com/archive/072417p24.shtml>

Jakubowski, J. M. Cundiff, and K. A. Matthews, (2018). "Cumulative childhood adversity and adult cardiometabolic disease: a meta-analysis," *Health Psychology*, vol. 37, no. 8, pp. 701-715.

Jimenez, E.C. (2020). Motivating factors of teachers in developing supplementary learning materials. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 8 (5), 108-113. <https://doi.org/10.21474/IJAR01/10912>

Jopling, A. Tracy, and J. LeMoult, (2020). "Childhood maltreatment, negative self-referential processing, and depressive symptoms during stress," *Psychological Research and Behavior Management*, vol. 13, no. 13, pp. 79-87.

Lane K., Teng M. Y., Barnes S. J., Moore K., Smith K., Lee M. (2018). Using appreciative inquiry to understand the role of teaching practices in student well-being at a research-intensive university. *The Canadian Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 9(2), 1-8.

Lara, L and Saracostti, M. (2019). Effect of Parental Involvement on Children's Academic Achievement in Chile. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. Retrieved January 31, 2023 from [frontiersin.org.https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369479747_Lack_of_Parental_Support_Unfavourable_in_Leading_to_Progression](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369479747_Lack_of_Parental_Support_Unfavourable_in_Leading_to_Progression)

Larson, K. E., Bradshaw, C. P., Rosenberg, M. S., & Day-Vines, N. L. (2018). Examining how proactive management and culturally

- responsive teaching relate to student behavior. School Psychology Review, 47(2), 153–166. Doi:10.17105/SPR-2017-0070.V47-2
- Le Poire et al. (2019). Guardianship: Parental Communication and Students Participation in School Activities. International Journal of Social Science Research 8(2):116. DOI:10.5296/ijssr.v8i2.16791
- Lincoln, Y., Lynham, S., & Guba, E. (2011). Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences, revisited. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Sage Handbook of qualitative research* (pp. 97-128). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Lopes, J., & Oliveira, C. (2017). Classroom discipline: Theory and practice. In J. P. Bakken (Ed.), *Classrooms: Academic content and behaviour strategy instruction for students with and without disabilities* (pp. 231–253). Nova Science Publishers. [Google Scholar].
- Nikku and Azman (2017). Breaking the cycle of child abuse in Malaysia: linking mandatory reporting, service delivery monitoring and review capacity mechanisms. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324750223_Breaking_the_cycle_of_child_abuse_in_Malaysia_linking_mandatory_reportin_g_service_delivery_monitoring_and_review_capacity_mechanisms
- Mathews, R. Pacella, M. P. Dunne, M. Simunovic, and C. Marston, (2020). “Improving measurement of child abuse and neglect: a systematic review and analysis of national prevalence studies,” *PLoS One*, vol. 15, no. 1, article e0227884.
- Matthysen (2021). <https://www.children.org/child-protection-policy>.
- Merriam Webster Dictionary (2023). <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/implementation>.
- Millapre, L. (2014) as cited by Castino, L. (2023). Child protection policy and behavioral management practices at a public elementary school in Rizal, Philippines. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Applied Business and Education*.
- Mittleman, J. (2018). A downward spiral? Childhood suspension and the path to juvenile arrest. *Sociology of Education*, 91, 183–204.
- Mulani, S. (2019). Relationship of transformational leadership of school principle and teacher discipline with the quality of education services. *JKP 2*, 205–222. Doi: 10.22236/jkpuhamka.v2i1.3815.
- Mulunge, M.M. (2010). Persistent socio-economic and Political dilemmas to the implementation of the 1989 United Nation Convention on the rights of the child in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 34, 10-
- Münger, Ann-Charlotte, and Ann-Marie Markström (2019). “School and Child Protection Services Professionals’ Views on the School’s Mission and Responsibilities for Children Living with Domestic Violence – Tensions and Gaps.” *Journal of Family Violence*, vol. 34, 2019, pp. 385-398.
- Munro, E. (2019). Decision-making under uncertainty in child protection: Creating a just and learning culture *Child & Family Social Work*, 24 (1), 123-130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.12589>
- Mustikasari, Nadya Ayu, and Dewi Rostyaningsih (2020). “Evaluation of Children Protection Policy from Violent Acts in Semarang City.” *Journal Of public Policy and Management Review*, Vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1-15.
- McCafferty P. (2021) ‘Children’s participation in child welfare decision making: Recognising dichotomies, conceptualising critically informed solutions’, *Child Care in Practice*.
- Mclean, Miriam J., et al. (2016). “Pre-Existing Adversity, Level of Child Protection Involvement, And School Attendance Predict Educational Outcomes in a Longitudinal Study.” *Child Abuse & Neglect*, vol. 51, 2016, pp. 120-131.
- Parton, Nigel (2016). “The Contemporary Politics of Child Protection: Part Two (the BASPCAN Founder’s Lecture 2015).” *Child Abuse Review*, vol 25, no. 1, 2015, pp. 9-16.
- Patzer, R. (2020, February). Sharing good practice: Strategies to Encourage Teacher Collaboration. *Irconnect.Com*. Retrieved From: <https://bit.ly/3cdk9bq>
- People’s Republic of China Ministry of Justice (2019). Fact Sheet: Children’s Protection Act of 2021 (H.R. 3716). <https://campaignforchildren.org/resources/fact-sheet/fact-sheet-childrens-protection-act-of-2021-h-r-3716/>
- Pekarsky, Alicia R. (2022). Overview of Child Maltreatment. <https://www.merckmanuals.com/professional/pediatrics/child-maltreatment/overview-of-child-maltreatment>.
- Pereira, P., and Ravasio, M. (2021). INDISCIPLINA NA RELAO PROFESSOR/ALUNO- CONTEXTO de UMA PESQUISA INTERVENO/INDISCIPLINE in the teacher/student relationship – context of an intervention research. *Braz. J. Dev.* 7, 4641–4648. Doi: 10.34117/bjdv7n1-315.
- Prestoza, M. J. (2022). 3ES (Explore Enlighten Exercise) learning worksheet: Its’effects to the academic performance in identifying research problems among senior high school. *International Journal of Arts, Sciences and Education*, 3(1), 166-173. <https://ijase.org/index.php/ijase/article/view/105>

- Quirto, L. & Santos, E. (2021). Child protection practices and classroom discipline in elementary schools. *Globus Journal of Progressive Education A Refereed Research Journal*.
- Rahman, Nur, and Sarip (2020). "Child Protection Policy for Victims of Sexual Crimes." *Varia Justicia*, vol. 16, no. 1, 2020, pp. 16-30.
- Ringel JS, Schultz D, Mendelsohn J, Holliday SB, Sieck K, Edochie I, Davis L.(2018). Improving Child Welfare Outcomes: Balancing Investments in Prevention and Treatment. *Rand Health Q. Mar*;7(4):4.
- Robles, A., Gjelsvik, A., Hirway, P., Vivier, P. M., High, P. (2019). Adverse childhood experiences and protective factors with school engagement. *Pediatrics*, 144(2), e20182945. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2018-2945>.
- Roche, Steven (2017). Child protection and maltreatment in the Philippines: A systematic review of the literature. *Asia & the Pacific Policy Studies*, 4(1), 104-128, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app5.167>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354424411_Local_child_protection_in_the_Philippines_A_case_study_of_actors_processes_and_key_risks_for_children
- Roche, S. (2019). Childhoods in policy: A critical analysis of national child protection policy in the Philippines. *Children & Society*, 33(2), 95-110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12295>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354424411_Local_child_protection_in_the_Philippines_A_case_study_of_actors_processes_and_key_risks_for_children
- Roche et al., (2021); UNICEF (2016).Roche, S., Flynn, C., & Mendes, P (2021). They became my second family’: Children’s relational lives and relationship-based practice in residential care in the Philippines. *Child & Family Social Work*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ch12846>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354424411_Local_child_protection_in_the_Philippines_A_case_study_of_actors_processes_and_key_risks_for_children.
- Saragih, K., and Mardianto, (2019). Relationship between teacher professional performance and discipline of workers with teacher professionalism in madrasah Tsanawiyah in Pematangsiantar City. *BILAEJ* 1, 77–84. Doi: 10.33258/biolae.v1i2.66.
- Sousa, W. A. Mason, T. I. Herrenkohl, D. Prince, R. C. Herrenkohl, and M. J. Russo, (2018). "Direct and indirect effects of child abuse and environmental stress: a lifecourse perspective on adversity and depressive symptoms," *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, vol. 88, no. 2, pp. 180–188.
- Souders, B. (2019). Positive Reinforcement for Kids: 11+ Examples for Parents. Retrieved November 13, 2022, from <https://positivepsychology.com/parenting-positivereinforcement/>
- Soriano, (2020). Depression central: tell me all I need to know about depression, *Psycom*. <https://www.psycom.net/depression.central.html>.
- Shokair and E. Abo Hamza, (2020). "Family violence and its impact on children’s mental health during COVID-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Educational Studies (IJITES)*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 2682–3926.
- Smetana JG., (2017). Current research on parenting styles, dimensions, and beliefs. *Curr Opin Psychol*. Vol.15:19–25. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Tanoue K, Senda M, An B, Tasaki M, Taguchi M, Kobashi K, Oana S, Mizoguchi F, Shiraishi Y, Yamada F, Okuyama M, Ichikawa K.N(2018). survey of hospital child protection teams in Japan. *Child Abuse Negl*.May;79:11-21.
- Ulug, M., Ozden, M. S., & Eryilmaz, A. (2017). The effects of Teachers’ attitudes on students’ personality and performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 738-742.
- Vardigan, (2019). Yelling at children (verbal abuse). <https://consumer.healthday.com/encyclopedia/children-s-health-10/child-development-news-124/yelling-at-children-verbal-abuse-648565.html>
- Vrolijk-Bosschaart TF, Brilleslijper-Kater SN, Benninga MA, Lindauer RJL, Teeuw AH, (2018). Clinical practice: recognizing child sexual abuse-what makes it so difficult? *Eur J Pediatr*.Sep;177(9):1343-1350.
- Ward KP, Lee SJ. (2020). Mothers’ and fathers’ parenting stress, responsiveness, and child well-being among low-income families. *Child Youth Serv Rev*. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Wesley, Carol (2020). Protective Factors to Promote Well-being and Prevent Child Abuse and Neglect- Child Welfare Information Gateway. <https://www.childwelfare.gov/topics/preventing/promoting/protectfactors/>
- Wesley, (2020). Protective Factors to Promote Well-being and Prevent Child Abuse and Neglect-Child Welfare Information Gateway. <https://www.childwelfare.gov/topics/preventing/promoting/protectfactors/>
- Wood JN, Henry MK, Berger RP, Lindberg DM, Anderst JD, Song L, Localio R, Feudtner C(2019). Use and Utility of Skeletal Surveys

to Evaluate for Occult Fractures in Young Injured Children. *Acad Pediatr*. May-Jun;19(4):428-437.

World Health Organization (2020). Child mal- treatment fact sheet. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3viQ7zZ>

Xiang, W. Wang, and F. Guan, (2019). “The relationship between child maltreatment and dispositional envy and the mediating effect of self-esteem and social support in young adults,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 9.

Yang Y, Johnstone H, Xue H, Rozelle, (2021). Infant cognitive development and stimulating parenting practices in rural China. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. Vol.18:5277. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

Yayasan Sayangi Tunas Cilik, 2019, Kebijakan Keselamatan Anak, YSTC: Jakarta

Yenny, AS, (2019). “Legal Protection of Teachers Justice in Pontianak City,” vol. 3, no. pp. 153–164, 2019, Doi: 10.32501/jhmb.V3i2.105

Zeanah CH, Humphreys KL (2018). Child Abuse and Neglect. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. Sep;57(9):637-644.

Zhang H., Li Y., Shi R., Dong P., Wang W. (2021). Prevalence of child maltreatment during the COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional survey of Rural Hubei, China. *British Journal of Social Work*. 10.1093/bjsw/bcab162 [CrossRef]

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